

Power and The Politics of Infrastructure Planning: A Case Study of The Proposed Construction of A High-Speed Rail System in Texas

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores challenges faced by the Texas high-speed rail project on social fronts, focusing on power dynamics and political consequences in infrastructure planning. The research aims to illuminate decision-making processes, stakeholder roles, and the impact of political and economic factors on infrastructure planning. Employing a research approach, data from news, media, and academic sources are analysed to investigate power dynamics and the political landscape surrounding Texas's high-speed rail system. The study's findings emphasize the significant power and influence held by private entities such as Texas Central Partners, driving the ambitious rail venture. Additionally, the research underscores the intricate relationships and power struggles among stakeholders—private companies, state governments, interest groups, and local communities—throughout the infrastructure planning journey. The study proposes actionable recommendations derived from research outcomes, intended to guide improved practices in infrastructure planning. Ultimately, this investigation enhances comprehension of power dynamics and political aspects in infrastructure planning, particularly concerning Texas's proposed high-speed rail system. The insights presented carry implications for policymakers, practitioners, and researchers engaged in infrastructure planning and development. With a focus on fostering fairness and environmental responsibility, this study aspires to provide valuable insights into the nature of power dynamics, facilitating sound infrastructure planning practices.

Keywords: *Power dynamics, Infrastructure planning, High-speed rail system, Transportation*

SARI PATI

Makalah ini mengeksplorasi tantangan yang dihadapi oleh proyek kereta berkecepatan tinggi Texas di bidang sosial, dengan fokus pada dinamika kekuasaan dan konsekuensi politik dalam perencanaan infrastruktur. Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk menjelaskan proses pengambilan keputusan, peran pemangku kepentingan, dan dampak faktor politik dan ekonomi terhadap perencanaan infrastruktur. Dengan menggunakan pendekatan penelitian, data dari berita, media, dan sumber akademis dianalisis untuk menyelidiki dinamika kekuasaan dan lanskap politik seputar sistem kereta api berkecepatan tinggi Texas. Temuan penelitian ini menekankan kekuatan dan pengaruh signifikan yang dimiliki oleh entitas swasta seperti Texas Central Partners, yang mendorong usaha kereta api yang ambisius. Selain itu, penelitian ini menggarisbawahi hubungan rumit dan perebutan kekuasaan di antara para pemangku kepentingan—perusahaan swasta, pemerintah negara bagian, kelompok kepentingan, dan komunitas lokal—sepanjang perjalanan perencanaan infrastruktur. Studi ini mengusulkan rekomendasi yang dapat ditindaklanjuti berdasarkan hasil penelitian, yang dimaksudkan untuk memandu perbaikan praktik perencanaan infrastruktur. Pada akhirnya, penyelidikan ini meningkatkan pemahaman tentang dinamika kekuasaan dan aspek politik dalam perencanaan infrastruktur, khususnya mengenai sistem kereta api kecepatan tinggi yang diusulkan di Texas. Wawasan yang disajikan membawa implikasi bagi pembuat kebijakan, praktisi, dan peneliti yang terlibat dalam perencanaan dan pembangunan

infrastruktur. Dengan fokus pada pengembangan keadilan dan tanggung jawab lingkungan, studi ini bertujuan untuk memberikan wawasan berharga mengenai sifat dinamika kekuasaan, memfasilitasi praktik perencanaan infrastruktur yang baik.

Kata Kunci: Dinamika kekuasaan, Perencanaan infrastruktur, Sistem kereta api kecepatan tinggi, Transportasi, Politik

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INTRODUCTION

The U.S. Census Bureau stated that Texas is the second largest state in the u s in terms of land area and population with over 30 million residents (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). As the population and economy expand transportation infrastructure planning becomes vital for meeting the needs of its people and businesses the Texas department of transportation is responsible for managing the State's transportation system including roads highways bridges and airports The majority of TxDOT's 31.5 billion budget for fiscal year 2022 comes from state and federal funds toll roads and public private partnerships (TxDOT, 2021). The Texas clear lanes initiative started in 2015 by the State's transportation commission aims to upgrade the transport network in the five biggest cities of Texas Austin Dallas Fort Worth Houston and San Antonio these urban areas have more than two thirds of the state's residents and 97 of its traffic jammed roads (TxDOT, 2016). The initiative is funded by proposition 1 and proposition 7 which the voters of Texas passed in 2014 and 2015 for non-toll transport projects (SUBCUSA, 2020).

Texas is a vast and rapidly expanding state that faces many challenges in planning and developing its transport network which includes roads highways public transportation rail lines airports ports and waterways (Kevin McPherson, Jessica Donald, & Bruce Wright, 2018). Transportation network is essential for the economic growth mobility security and wellbeing

of Texans (Kevin McPherson et al., 2018). By 2050 the State's population will increase by at least 50 to over 54 million according to the Texas office of the state demographer emphasizing the need for substantial growth and enhancement of its transportation network.

Roads and highways are a key element of Texas transportation network the state has almost 314 000 miles of roads and highways more than any other state (Kevin McPherson et al., 2018). About a quarter of this network is part of the state highway system while local governments oversee the rest both passenger and commercial vehicles use these roads and highways causing wear and tear on pavement and bridges (Kevin McPherson et al., 2018). From 2010 to 2016 the total daily distance travelled by vehicles rose by 15 5 mainly because of population growth and economic development (Kevin McPherson et al., 2018). Texas cities are struggling with increased traffic and longer travel times with the Texas a m transportation institute (TTI) estimating that traffic congestion cost city drivers between 494 and nearly 1 500 per person in 2014 (Kevin McPherson et al., 2018).

Public transportation systems, such as buses and light rail, are a vital part of Texas' transportation infrastructure. These systems offer alternatives to driving, help reduce congestion, and cater to those without access to a car or who prefer not to drive. In fiscal 2019, Texas public transportation riders took over 274 million trips using various

transit modes (Jessica Donald & Shannon Halbrook, 2021).

Texas has done some good things to deal with transportation infrastructure planning challenges. The Texas Innovation Alliance, a partnership between TxDOT, academic institutions, and private companies, works to create and use new transportation technologies and solutions (TxDOT, 2020). The state has also set up Regional Transportation Councils (RTC) to work together on transportation planning among local governments and stakeholders in different regions (TxDOT, 2020). Plus, Texas has adopted the Texas Transportation Plan (TTP) 2050, which is TxDOT's long-term, performance-based transportation plan guiding planning and programming decisions for the statewide multimodal transportation system for the next 30 years. According to TTP 2050, keeping Texas' transportation modes in good shape would need an estimated \$547 billion in state and federal funding by 2040 (TxDOT, 2023).

Transportation infrastructure planning in Texas is a complicated process that needs coordination among various agencies organizations and stakeholders the state has done some programs and policies to tackle transportation infrastructure development and improvement challenges but there are still issues and opportunities for innovation remain challenges include funding gaps environmental impacts social equity concerns and changing travel patterns opportunities involve emerging technologies like autonomous vehicles smart mobility solutions such as ride hailing services and integrated data platforms like mobility as a service (MaaS).

High speed rail systems have been proposed in different regions of the United States for decades but their implementation has been limited due to challenges like high costs regulatory obstacles and political opposition (Matt McFarland, 2020). The first attempts to introduce modern

high-speed rail in the United States began in 1965 in response to advancements in Japanese rail technology (Peterman, 2013). Legislation enacted that year allowed trains to operate at speeds exceeding 100 miles per hour on the route between New York and Washington, DC (Matt McFarland, 2020). However, the progress of high-speed rail was hindered as the railway industry experienced a decline in the 1970s (Matt McFarland, 2020).

Despite these challenges there have been ongoing efforts to develop high speed rail systems in the United States (Matt McFarland, 2020). Amtrak was established in 1971 with its goal being the provision of rail services, for passengers between cities (Peterman, 2013). However, it has faced challenges in achieving the level of speed and efficiency as high-speed rail systems in parts of the world (Peterman, 2013).

In times there have been proposals for high-speed rail projects within the United States (Texas Central, 2023). One such project is the Texas high speed rail initiative which aims to connect Dallas and Houston through a 240-mile line that would enable travel at speeds of up to 205 miles per hour (Texas Central, 2023). This undertaking has encountered obstacles including opposition from residents and lawmakers (Baruch Feigenbaum, 2023; Texas Central, 2023). Nevertheless, it has also received support, from business and civic leaders who view it as a means to reduce travel durations and stimulate growth (Texas Central, 2023).

One of the significant challenges faced by high-speed rail projects in the United States is securing funding. While the federal government has provided some support in the past, it has been relatively modest compared to the substantial costs involved in developing and constructing a high-speed rail system (Wendell Cox, 2022). To address this issue, efforts have been made

to attract funding for the Texas project, which has achieved some level of success. However, additional funding will still be necessary to complete the project (Texas Central, 2023).

The vision of connecting Dallas and Houston, as proposed by the Texas Central Railway (TCR), comes with an estimated budget of around \$20 billion (Texas Central, 2023). This project aims to heavily rely on private investment sources, representing a unique approach to infrastructure financing in the US. Traditionally, large-scale infrastructure projects in the country have depended on a mix of public and private funds. However, the TCR initiative's decision not to seek public subsidies has significant implications for the future of infrastructure financing.

Understanding the dynamics of securing such a substantial amount from private sources can serve as a blueprint or a cautionary tale for other states or regions considering similar endeavors. The vested interest of Texas Central Partners LLC as a primary investor highlights a significant reliance on corporate stakeholders, potentially reshaping the funding landscape for future infrastructure projects in the US. Analyzing this model will be crucial in determining its viability and potential for replication.

another challenge that the project grapple with significant regulatory challenges. Overseeing these endeavours, the Federal Railroad Administration (FRA) ensures they adhere to a plethora of regulations, a process acknowledged by the (U.S. Department of Transportation, 2023) as both time-consuming and costly. Alongside the FRA, the Texas Department of Transportation and the Texas Commission on Environmental Quality play pivotal roles in shaping the regulatory landscape for this ambitious rail system in Texas.

These regulatory dynamics aren't just about ticking boxes. They aim to ascertain that such

rail systems are compliant, safe, efficient, and environmentally responsible. However, navigating these waters can be a daunting task, as the Texas Central Railway project has learned the hard way. From lawmakers questioning its viability and safety to the Environmental Protection Agency's denial of their preferred station site in downtown Houston, it's clear that bureaucratic obstacles can pose significant threats to infrastructure development (Federal Railroad Administration, 2021).

Peeling back the layers of these challenges reveals an intricate dance of federal and state regulations. Yet, it also offers an opportunity: to streamline the approval processes and ensure that vital infrastructure projects thrive without getting ensnared in regulatory snares. Finding the right balance is essential for the future success and expansion of high-speed rail systems across the country.

Understanding the intricate dance of power and influence is of utmost importance, not only for the stakeholders involved in a project but also for any region considering similar large-scale infrastructure endeavors. This understanding becomes particularly crucial when examining the power dynamics and politics surrounding infrastructure planning, such as the high-speed rail system in Texas. By delving deep into the stakeholders involved in the Texas high-speed rail system, this research aims to shed light on the complex dynamics of power and decision-making within infrastructure planning.

Furthermore, this study seeks to contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the economic factors that shape infrastructure projects. By unraveling the influence of these factors, policymakers and corporate entities can gain valuable insights into effective communication, negotiation, and consensus-building techniques. This knowledge can inform future infrastructure projects and help ensure their success.

The implications of this research extend beyond the transportation industry and into the realm of urban planning. By examining the delicate balance between advocacy by entities like the Texas Central Partners and opposition from community members and environmental bodies, policymakers and corporate entities can make more informed decisions regarding infrastructure development. This holistic approach to studying the power and politics of infrastructure planning will undoubtedly provide valuable insights for both the transportation industry and urban planning as a whole.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Power and politics in infrastructure planning

Infrastructure planning involves making decisions about the design, funding, and implementation of projects that can have significant economic, social, and environmental impacts on communities. As such, infrastructure planning is often influenced by power dynamics and political interests (Pinzur, 2021). In this section, we will discuss the role of power and politics in infrastructure planning, drawing on relevant literature.

(Bent Flyvbjerg, 2002) emphasizes the nature of infrastructure planning and highlights the influence of power dynamics on shaping decisions regarding projects. Power can be wielded by a range of actors, including government officials, private companies, interest groups and local communities. Due, to their differing objectives and priorities these actors often find themselves engaged in conflicts and negotiations when it comes to making infrastructure planning choices.

Similarly, (Pløger, 2021) argue that Infrastructure planning is a political process that involves a complex interplay of power relations, institutional arrangements, and public participation. Public participation in

infrastructure planning can be promoted by a public authority and especially those with a higher stake (Bobbio, 2018). However, an increase in the level or frequency of public participation does not automatically lead to better outcomes (Schweizer et al., 2016). The success of new institutional arrangements for more inclusive and pro-poor participatory governance will depend largely on existing power relations (John Gaventa, 2003).

In addition, (Stone, 1989) argues that infrastructure planning is shaped by the broader political context in which it takes place. He suggests that political institutions, such as electoral systems and party systems, can influence infrastructure planning decisions by shaping the distribution of power and interests among different groups.

Power and politics can have significant implications for equity and social justice in infrastructure planning (Laurie A. Shuster, 2021). Addressing social inequities may require attention not only to how the funds are distributed, but also what the funds are used for (Melissa L. Finucane, Jaime Madrigano, & Jhacova Williams, 2021). Differential resilience across groups or places relates to both physical or built infrastructure (reliable and safe electricity, transport, schools, etc.) as well as social infrastructure (e.g., government functions, educational programs, social support networks).

Overall, the literature suggests that power and politics play a significant role in infrastructure planning infrastructure planning decisions are influenced by the goals and priorities of different actors as well as broader political and institutional contexts these power dynamics can have implications for equity and social justice highlighting the need for more inclusive and participatory planning processes.

Theoretical frameworks for analysing power in infrastructure planning

Infrastructure planning involves complex power dynamics, as various actors with different goals and interests vie for influence in decision-making processes. There are several theoretical frameworks that can be used to analyse power in infrastructure planning, including the following:

- *Actor-Network Theory (ANT)*
Actor-Network Theory (ANT) is a sociological framework that emphasizes the role of non-human actors (such as technology and infrastructure) in shaping social relations and power dynamics. In the context of infrastructure planning, ANT can be used to analyse how infrastructure projects act as mediators of power relations between various actors (Latour, 2007).
- *Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA)*
Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) is an approach to analysing language and communication that emphasizes the role of power relations in shaping discourse. In the context of infrastructure planning, CDA can be used to analyse how language and communication are used to legitimize certain actors and interests over others (Fairclough, 2013).
- *Political Ecology*
Political ecology is an interdisciplinary field that examines the relationships between nature society and power in the context of infrastructure planning political ecology can be used to analyze how infrastructure projects impact the environment and how power relations between various actors shape environmental outcomes (Bryant, Raymond L, & Sinead Bailey, 1997).
- *Institutional Analysis and Development (IAD)*
The Institutional Analysis and Development (IAD) framework serves as a tool to examine how institutions influence the orchestration of group endeavors and processes of decision-making within the realm of

infrastructure planning. This framework enables the exploration of how regulatory setups and administrative formations, as part of institutional configurations, exert influence on dynamics of authority and the course of decision-making processes (Ostrom, 1990).

- *Foucauldian Power Analysis*
Foucauldian Power Analysis is a theoretical framework that emphasizes the role of power in shaping social relations and institutions. In the context of infrastructure planning, Foucauldian Power Analysis can be used to analyse how power is exercised through various mechanisms such as discipline, surveillance, and normalization. It can help identify power structures, power relations, and power struggles among different actors involved in infrastructure planning (Foucault, 2012).
- *Social Network Analysis (SNA)*
Social Network Analysis (SNA) is a framework that examines the relationships between actors in a network. In the context of infrastructure planning, SNA can be used to analyse how actors are connected and how power is distributed within the network. It can help identify influential actors and key decision-makers in infrastructure planning processes (Borgatti, Stephen P, Martin G, Everett, & Jeffrey C, 2018).

Overall, these theoretical frameworks offer valuable tools for analysing power dynamics in infrastructure planning. Each framework provides a unique lens through which to examine power relations among actors involved in infrastructure planning processes. By applying these frameworks, researchers can gain a deeper understanding of the complex power dynamics at play and help identify ways to address power imbalances and promote more equitable infrastructure planning outcomes.

Review of related studies on Power and the politics and high-speed rail systems

High speed rail systems according to the Asian Development Bank (ADB), are intricate infrastructure projects that include a wide range of stakeholders including governmental organizations private investors and the general public as a result power dynamics play a significant role in shaping decision-making processes related to the planning funding and implementation of high-speed rail systems (Bugalia, Misra, Mahalingam, & Seetha Ram, 2022). Several studies have explored the power dynamics involved in high-speed rail planning and implementation as well as their impact on project outcomes.

For example, (B Flyvbjerg, Bruzelius, & Rothengatter, 2003) analysed the power dynamics involved in high-speed rail planning in Europe and found that decision making was dominated by a small group of actors often to the detriment of the public interest power disparities according to his argument can result. (Minn, 2013) in his research explored the political and economic factors that have influenced the development of high-speed rail in the United States the author analysed the role of federal and state governments interest groups and private companies in shaping high speed rail policy and funding. The paper also covers the difficulties high-speed rail projects encounter in the US, including as opposition from the general public and finance issues.

Ma Xiao argues that China's success in building a high-speed rail network is due in large part to its ability to impose a standardized design across the country (MA, 2022). According to Ma Xiao's book "Localized Bargaining: The Political Economy of China's High-Speed Railway Program", China's high-speed rail program was shaped by bottom-up, localized bargaining on the part of territorial governments (MA, 2022).

According to an article by the Asian Development Bank, the success of high-speed rail systems in Southeast Asia depends on factors such as political stability, institutional capacity, and cross-border cooperation (Hayashi, Rothengatter, & Seetha Ram, 2021). High-speed rail development has been recognized as an important policy tool for regional development around the world, notably in Asia and Europe (Hayashi et al., 2021).

In a study on China's infrastructure diplomacy, it was found that power dynamics and political institutions play a role in shaping policies and outcomes (Oh, 2018). The study argues that the relative bargaining power of a host country is influenced by its threat points, which interact with the project.

METHODOLOGY

Research design and approach

The research design for this study is a case study design, as it focuses on a specific case - the proposed construction of a high-speed rail system in Texas - and seeks to explore the power dynamics and political factors that influence infrastructure planning in this context. The approach taken was a qualitative one, relying on analysis of existing data and documents to explore these issues.

Data collection methods:

Since this research is based on secondary data only, the data collection methods will focus on gathering existing data and documents related to the proposed construction of the high-speed rail system in Texas. This could include:

News, articles, and media coverage related to the proposed high-speed rail system

Academic literature and studies related to infrastructure planning, power dynamics, and political factors in transportation infrastructure development

Research Questions:

- (1) How do power dynamics factor into the process of strategizing and reaching determinations pertaining to the Texas high-speed rail infrastructure?
- (2) What duties and functions do stakeholders engaged in the Texan high-speed rail system, such as corporations, state administrations, advocacy factions, and nearby populations, undertake?
- (3) How do political and economic considerations exert sway over the delineation and verdict-forming mechanisms intertwined with the Texan high-speed rail setup?

Case Study: Proposed High-Speed Rail System in Texas description and background

The Texas Central Railway (TCR) envisions linking Dallas and Houston, two prominent Texan urban hubs, through a high-speed rail network currently under construction as an integral element of the TCR initiative. This ambitious undertaking holds the promise of enabling commuters to traverse the distance between these two cities within approximately 90 minutes, courtesy of the integration of Japan's proven and secure Shinkansen technology. The financial blueprint for the endeavor approximates \$20 billion, with the complete capital infusion anticipated to be mobilized from private investment sources (Texas Central, 2023). The prospective appellation for this envisaged high-speed rail infrastructure in Texas is recognized as the Texas High-Speed Rail system.

Stakeholder analysis

In the case of the proposed high-speed rail system in Texas, the stakeholders can be broadly categorized into four groups:

- (1) **Advocates:** This category encompasses individuals and groups who express support for the endeavour due to its anticipated advantages, such as enhanced rapid transit, job opportunities, and

bolstered economic development. Backers of the initiative consist of entities like the Texas Association of Business, the Greater Houston Partnership, and the North Texas Commission.

- (2) **Opposing Parties:** Within this faction, you'll find individuals and organizations that hold reservations about the initiative, citing potential downsides like heightened noise, disturbance to local neighbourhoods, and adverse ecological effects. Critics of the project involve certain community members, property proprietors, and environmental advocacy bodies.
- (3) **Governmental Bodies:** This segment covers various federal, state, and local governmental agencies that bear responsibilities in overseeing, financing, or granting approval to the scheme. The Federal Railroad Administration, the Texas Department of Transportation, and the Texas Commission on Environmental Quality constitute key governmental players engaged in the proposed high-speed rail route in Texas.
- (4) **Financial Backers:** This grouping pertains to non-public entities that have injected funds into the endeavour and hold a vested financial interest in its triumph. Texas Central Partners LLC stands as the primary investor in the proposed high-speed rail system in Texas.

Power dynamics and actors involved in the project

The decision-making process concerning the high-speed rail initiative in Texas embodies a complex interplay of power dynamics involving diverse entities with distinct interests and viewpoints. Central to this are the Texas Central Partners (TCP), a private enterprise that instigated and funded the endeavor; the state government, holding jurisdiction over project regulation and endorsement; and assorted interest collectives such as ecological associations, landholders,

and local administrations, each voicing concerns or reservations. TCP stands as the principal advocate of the initiative, channelling substantial financial resources into its evolution and advocacy. Collaborative efforts with state and federal authorities have also been undertaken to facilitate its realization. However, the venture has encountered resistance from certain municipal bodies, citizens, and land proprietors, who harbour apprehensions regarding potential repercussions on property values, safety, and overall well-being. Additionally, some freight rail lines have opposed the project's signalling system because it would interfere with their existing communications technology (Baruch Feigenbaum, 2023).

The project has also faced legal and environmental challenges that have delayed its completion. For example, the Environmental Protection Agency refused to approve TCP's preferred station in downtown Houston, forcing it to relocate its southern terminus to the western suburbs (Baruch Feigenbaum, 2023). The project's status and future remain uncertain as of 2023.

Power struggles have undeniably left their mark on the project's development, as various parties have engaged in a relentless battle for influence and control over the decision-making process. The Texas Central Partners have unyieldingly sought to exert their sway through extensive lobbying endeavours and leveraging their substantial financial resources. Concurrently, interest groups, driven by a steadfast determination, have mobilized public opinion and applied relentless pressure on decision-makers through thought-provoking protests and other impactful forms of activism. These actors have demonstrated an unrelenting commitment to their respective causes, engaging in an intricate dance of power and influence that has shaped the trajectory of the project.

Impacts and implications of the high-speed rail system

The proposed high-speed rail system in Texas has stirred up a whirlwind of potential impacts and implications, both positive and negative, for the diverse range of stakeholders involved. One glimmer of positivity lies in the promise of a swifter and more efficient mode of transportation for individuals shuttling between major cities in Texas. The envisioned benefits include potential economic gains and a potential reduction in the vexing problem of traffic congestion that plagues highways and airports. Yet, amid these optimistic prospects, concerns loom large regarding the potential harm inflicted upon nearby communities and the environment. These concerns encompass the disturbing spectre of displacement, disruption of the delicate ecosystem, and the upheaval of countless animal habitats.

Notably, a study conducted by the esteemed Texas A&M Transportation Institute (Chipindula, Du, Botlaguduru, Choe, & Kommalapati, 2022), has unveiled a host of economic benefits that the proposed high-speed rail system could yield. These include the much-desired creation of employment opportunities, a surge in economic activity, and even environmental advantages stemming from reduced carbon emissions and the mitigation of traffic congestion. Nevertheless, some research has set off warning signals, sparking concerns about the project's possible consequences, especially for rural communities and the environment. It is imperative to acknowledge that the impacts and intricacies tied to the high-speed rail system are intricately intertwined with the intricate realm of power dynamics and the intricate decision-making procedures enveloping the initiative. As previously stated, a multitude of entities are engaged in this intricate scenario, each possessing a distinctive degree of authority and sway. The fate of the project hinges upon the stakeholders' ability to navigate the treacherous terrain of these power

dynamics, engaging in delicate negotiations and striving to make decisions that harmoniously balance the diverse array of interests at stake.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The planning and decision-making processes for Texas' high-speed rail system are governed by intricate and multifaceted power dynamics. Various actors, each wielding their own power and interests, shape the trajectory of this ambitious project. Among the main players are Texas Central Partners (TCP), a private company leading the development, the state government, which offers regulatory and financial support, interest groups such as environmentalists and landowners, and the local communities affected by the project.

One crucial aspect of power dynamics lies in the role of private companies like Texas Central Partners. With their substantial financial resources and political sway, these entities often hold disproportionate influence in decision-making processes. This holds true for the high-speed rail system in Texas, where TCP has invested millions of dollars and tirelessly lobbied for support from both state and federal authorities (Palash Ghosh, 2021). Moreover, TCP claims that the project will be privately funded, eschewing the need for public subsidies (Texas Central, 2023).

Equally significant is the impact of the state government on infrastructure planning and decision-making. State governments hold substantial sway over endeavours of this magnitude, exercising their impact via regulatory structures and financial modalities. In the context of Texas' high-speed rail infrastructure, the state government has assumed a central position, contributing funds and furnishing regulatory support. Notably, the government has granted approval for TCP's environmental impact statement—a crucial step in securing federal endorsement for the project (Texas Central, 2020).

Additionally, local communities and interest groups possess considerable power within the infrastructure planning and decision-making landscape. These stakeholders actively voice their concerns and exercise their influence through protests, legal challenges, and lobbying efforts. When it comes to the Texas high-speed rail system, these groups have raised valid worries regarding the potential impact on property values, safety, quality of life, and the environment. Some have even contested TCP's eminent domain authority and questioned the accuracy of its ridership projections in the court of law (Baruch Feigenbaum, 2023). By rallying their elected representatives, these groups seek to either oppose or support the project at various levels of government.

In essence, the power dynamics inherent in the infrastructure planning and decision-making process of the high-speed rail system in Texas are intricate and diverse. A plethora of stakeholders with differing levels of power and influence are at play, ensuring a complex interplay of interests and perspectives.

CONCLUSION

The power dynamics in infrastructure planning, particularly in the context of the proposed high-speed rail system in Texas, is evident that power plays a crucial role in shaping infrastructure planning processes and decision-making. Private companies, such as the Texas Central Partners, exert significant influence due to their financial resources and political connections. State governments also have a substantial role in supporting and regulating infrastructure projects. Interest groups and local communities voice their concerns and exert pressure through advocacy and activism. Additionally, political and economic factors strongly influence infrastructure planning and decision-making processes. The interplay between these stakeholders and dynamics significantly shapes the outcomes and direction of infrastructure projects.

Acknowledging and understanding the power dynamics among stakeholders is crucial for effective decision-making and ensuring the legitimacy of infrastructure projects. Public engagement and participation processes should be structured to include diverse perspectives and address power imbalances.

Furthermore, incorporating political and economic factors into the decision-making process is essential to avoid undue influence and ensure transparent and fair infrastructure planning. This includes considering the economic viability, cost-benefit analysis, and alignment with broader regional development goals.

To address the implications and recommendations derived from the study, infrastructure planning practices should adopt approaches that foster collaboration, information sharing,

and conflict resolution among stakeholders. Engaging in dialogues and negotiations involving multiple stakeholders can effectively address power dynamics and foster the cultivation of consensus. Furthermore, it remains of paramount importance to consistently appraise the societal, economic, and environmental repercussions associated with infrastructure undertakings, such as the high-speed rail system in Texas. To this end, it is imperative to establish robust monitoring and evaluation frameworks, enabling the scrutiny of enduring impacts and facilitating pertinent adaptations aimed at augmenting project results and ensuring its sustainability. By incorporating these implications and recommendations into infrastructure planning practice, decision-makers can navigate power dynamics, promote inclusive decision-making, and ensure the effectiveness and long-term success of infrastructure projects.

REFERENCES

- Baruch Feigenbaum. (2023). The current status of Texas Central's proposed high-speed rail line linking Dallas and Houston - Reason Foundation. Retrieved 28 April 2023, from <https://reason.org/policy-brief/the-current-status-of-texas-centrals-proposed-high-speed-rail-line-linking-dallas-and-houston/>
- Bobbio, L. (2018). Designing effective public participation. New Pub: Oxford University Press, 38(1), 41–57. Retrieved 28 April 2023 from <https://doi.org/10.1080/14494035.2018.1511193>
- Borgatti, Stephen P, Martin G, Everett, & Jeffrey C. (2018). Analyzing Social Networks - Stephen P Borgatti, Martin G Everett, Jeffrey C Johnson - Google Books. Sage. Retrieved 28 April 2023 from [https://books.google.co.id/books?hl=en&lr=&id=gpEDwAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&dq=Borgatti,+S.+P.,+Everett,+M.+G.,+%26+Johnson,+J.+C.+\(2009\).+Analyzing+social+networks.+Sage+publications.&ots=N-dfP22y5X&sig=0oVxs62aQYt8BQRnif1w8Xyi_0w&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false](https://books.google.co.id/books?hl=en&lr=&id=gpEDwAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&dq=Borgatti,+S.+P.,+Everett,+M.+G.,+%26+Johnson,+J.+C.+(2009).+Analyzing+social+networks.+Sage+publications.&ots=N-dfP22y5X&sig=0oVxs62aQYt8BQRnif1w8Xyi_0w&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false)
- Bryant, Raymond L, & Sinead Bailey. (1997). Third World Political Ecology - Raymond L. Bryant, Sinéad Bailey - Google Books. Psychology Press. Retrieved 28 April 2023 from [https://books.google.co.id/books?hl=en&lr=&id=T-6i5pVeQPUC&oi=fnd&pg=PR11&dq=Bryant,+R.+L.,+%26+Bailey,+S.+\(1997\).+Third+World+political+ecology.+Routledge.&ots=ZGK01_uLjz&sig=wncCly-qk-6SRtSAj1B05qxTrBs&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=Bryant%2C%20R.%20L.%2C%20%26%20Bailey%2C%20S.%20\(1997\).%20Third%20World%20political%20ecology.%20Routledge.&f=false](https://books.google.co.id/books?hl=en&lr=&id=T-6i5pVeQPUC&oi=fnd&pg=PR11&dq=Bryant,+R.+L.,+%26+Bailey,+S.+(1997).+Third+World+political+ecology.+Routledge.&ots=ZGK01_uLjz&sig=wncCly-qk-6SRtSAj1B05qxTrBs&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=Bryant%2C%20R.%20L.%2C%20%26%20Bailey%2C%20S.%20(1997).%20Third%20World%20political%20ecology.%20Routledge.&f=false)
- Bugalia, N., Misra, S., Mahalingam, A., & Seetha Ram, K. (2022). Policy Messages for Planning and Implementing High-Speed Rail in Asia. Retrieved 28 April 2023 from <https://doi.org/10.56506/PWXS1277>
- Chipindula, J., Du, H., Botlaguduru, V. S. V., Choe, D., & Kommalapati, R. R. (2022). Life cycle environmental impact of a high-speed rail system in the Houston-Dallas I-45 corridor. *Public Transport*, 14(2), 481–501. Retrieved 29 April 2023 from <https://doi.org/10.1007/S12469-021-00264-2/TABLES/6>
- Fairclough, N. (2013). Critical discourse analysis and critical policy studies. <http://Dx.Doi.Org/10.1080/19460171.2013.798239>, 7(2), 177–197. Retrieved 28 April 2023 from <https://doi.org/10.1080/19460171.2013.798239>
- Federal Railroad Administration. (2021). Bipartisan Infrastructure Law Information from FRA | FRA. Retrieved 28 April 2023,

from <https://railroads.dot.gov/BIL>

- Flyvbjerg, B, Bruzelius, N., & Rothengatter, W. (2003). *Megaprojects and Risk: An Anatomy of Ambition* - Bent Flyvbjerg, Nils Bruzelius, Werner Rothengatter - Google Books. Cambridge university press. Retrieved 28 April 2023 from [https://books.google.co.id/books?hl=en&lr=&id=RAV5P-50UjEC&oi=fnd&pg=PP8&dq=Flyvbjerg,+B.+\(2003\).+Megaprojects+and+risk:+An+anatomy+of+ambition.+Cambridge+University+Press.&ots=R_Bj2dd1eZ&sig=0xOSLdFQg9byaAHaV7qiilLuF2M&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=Flyvbjerg%2C%20B.%20\(2003\).%20Megaprojects%20and%20risk%3A%20An%20anatomy%20of%20ambition.%20Cambridge%20University%20Press.&f=false](https://books.google.co.id/books?hl=en&lr=&id=RAV5P-50UjEC&oi=fnd&pg=PP8&dq=Flyvbjerg,+B.+(2003).+Megaprojects+and+risk:+An+anatomy+of+ambition.+Cambridge+University+Press.&ots=R_Bj2dd1eZ&sig=0xOSLdFQg9byaAHaV7qiilLuF2M&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=Flyvbjerg%2C%20B.%20(2003).%20Megaprojects%20and%20risk%3A%20An%20anatomy%20of%20ambition.%20Cambridge%20University%20Press.&f=false)
- Flyvbjerg, Bent. (2002). Bringing Power to Planning Research. [Http://Dx.Doi.Org/10.1177/0739456X0202100401](http://Dx.Doi.Org/10.1177/0739456X0202100401), 21(4), 353–366. Retrieved 28 April 2023 from <https://doi.org/10.1177/0739456X0202100401>
- Foucault, M. (2012). *Discipline and Punish: The Birth of the Prison* - Michel Foucault - Google Books. Vintage. Retrieved 28 April 2023 from [https://books.google.co.id/books?hl=en&lr=&id=6rff0H5TsmYC&oi=fnd&pg=PP9&dq=Foucault,+M.+\(1977\).+Discipline+and+punish:+The+birth+of+the+prison.+Vintage.&ots=1OaZPVt073&sig=drslIURUARINmZp2JE0nkdcFNY&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false](https://books.google.co.id/books?hl=en&lr=&id=6rff0H5TsmYC&oi=fnd&pg=PP9&dq=Foucault,+M.+(1977).+Discipline+and+punish:+The+birth+of+the+prison.+Vintage.&ots=1OaZPVt073&sig=drslIURUARINmZp2JE0nkdcFNY&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false)
- Hayashi, Y., Rothengatter, W., & Seetha Ram, K. (2021). FRONTIERS IN HIGH-SPEED RAIL DEVELOPMENT. Retrieved from www.adbi.org
- Jessica Donald, & Shannon Halbrook. (2021). Public Transit in Texas. Retrieved 29 April 2023, from <https://comptroller.texas.gov/economy/fiscal-notes/2021/apr/transit.php>
- John Gaventa. (2003). Towards Participatory Local Governance: Assessing the Transformative Possibilities * Prepared for the Conference on Participation: From Tyranny to Transformation. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/240619950>
- Kevin McPherson, Jessica Donald, & Bruce Wright. (2018). Transportation Infrastructure: Keeping Texas Moving. Retrieved 29 April 2023, from <https://comptroller.texas.gov/economy/fiscal-notes/2018/may/transportation.php>
- Latour, B. (2007). *Reassembling the Social: An Introduction to Actor-Network-Theory* - Bruno Latour - Google Books. Oup Oxford,. Retrieved 28 April 2023 from [https://books.google.co.id/books?hl=en&lr=&id=BgJREAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PR7&dq=Latour,+B.+\(2005\).+Reassembling+the+social:+An+introduction+to+Actor-Network-Theory.+Oxford+University+Press.&ots=Z6lu3zBKTb&sig=eKEWa69_rDwuwZgg_GTIp_qDc5c&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=Latour%2C%20B.%20\(2005\).%20Reassembling%20the%20social%3A%20An%20introduction%20to%20Actor-Network-Theory.%20Oxford%20University%20Press.&f=false](https://books.google.co.id/books?hl=en&lr=&id=BgJREAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PR7&dq=Latour,+B.+(2005).+Reassembling+the+social:+An+introduction+to+Actor-Network-Theory.+Oxford+University+Press.&ots=Z6lu3zBKTb&sig=eKEWa69_rDwuwZgg_GTIp_qDc5c&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=Latour%2C%20B.%20(2005).%20Reassembling%20the%20social%3A%20An%20introduction%20to%20Actor-Network-Theory.%20Oxford%20University%20Press.&f=false)
- Laurie A. Shuster. (2021). What does infrastructure have to do with social justice and equity? | ASCE. Retrieved 28 April 2023, from <https://www.asce.org/publications-and-news/civil-engineering-source/civil-engineering-magazine/issues/magazine-issue/article/2021/11/what-does-infrastructure-have-to-do-with-social-justice-and-equity>
- MA, X. (2022). Localized Bargaining: The Political Economy of China's High-Speed Railway Program. Localized Bargaining. Oxford University Press. Retrieved 29 April 2023 from <https://doi.org/10.1093/OSO/9780197638910.001.0001>
- Matt McFarland. (2020). For American high-speed rail, 2020 could be a turning point | CNN Business. Retrieved 28 April 2023, from <https://edition.cnn.com/2020/07/08/energy/high-speed-rail-us/index.html>
- Melissa L. Finucane, Jaime Madrigano, & Jhacova Williams. (2021). Promoting Social Equity in Infrastructure Planning and Delivery | RAND. Retrieved 28 April 2023, from <https://www.rand.org/blog/2021/06/promoting-social-equity-in-infrastructure-planning.html>
- Minn, M. (2013). The Political Economy of High Speed Rail in the United States. [Http://Dx.Doi.Org/10.1080/17450101.2012.655973](http://Dx.Doi.Org/10.1080/17450101.2012.655973), 8(2), 185–200. Retrieved 28 April 2023 from <https://doi.org/10.1080/17450101.2012.655973>
- Oh, Y. A. (2018). Power asymmetry and threat points: negotiating China's infrastructure development in Southeast Asia. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09692290.2018.1447981>, 25(4), 530–552. Retrieved 29 April 2023 from <https://doi.org/10.1080/09692290.2018.1447981>
- Ostrom, E. (1990). *Governing the Commons: The Evolution of Institutions for Collective Action* - Elinor Ostrom - Google Books. Cambridge university press. Retrieved 28 April 2023 from [https://books.google.co.id/books?hl=en&lr=&id=4xg6oUobMz4C&oi=fnd&pg=PR11&dq=Ostrom,+E.+\(1990\).+Governing+the+commons:+The+evolution+of+institutions+for+collective+action.+Cambridge+University+Press.&ots=aPbqBKqKZg&sig=wtFpDQ8d39EXIRCqUtGZm89vDcI&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=Ostrom%2C%20E.%20\(1990\).%20Governing%20the%20commons%3A%20The%20evolution%20of%20institutions%20for%20collective%20action.%20Cambridge%20University%20Press.&f=false](https://books.google.co.id/books?hl=en&lr=&id=4xg6oUobMz4C&oi=fnd&pg=PR11&dq=Ostrom,+E.+(1990).+Governing+the+commons:+The+evolution+of+institutions+for+collective+action.+Cambridge+University+Press.&ots=aPbqBKqKZg&sig=wtFpDQ8d39EXIRCqUtGZm89vDcI&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=Ostrom%2C%20E.%20(1990).%20Governing%20the%20commons%3A%20The%20evolution%20of%20institutions%20for%20collective%20action.%20Cambridge%20University%20Press.&f=false)
- Palash Ghosh. (2021). High Speed Rail In Texas Will Connect Dallas To Houston. Retrieved 28 April 2023, from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/palashghosh/2021/06/15/first-high-speed-rail-in-us-will-connect-dallas-to-houston/?sh=26b42140278a>
- Peterman, D. R. (2013). The Development of High Speed Rail in the United States: Issues and Recent Events. Retrieved from www.crs.gov
- Pinzur, D. (2021). Infrastructural power: discretion and the dynamics of infrastructure in action. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17530350.2021.1913212>, 14(6), 644–661. Retrieved 28 April 2023 from <https://doi.org/10.1080/17530350.2021.1913212>
- Pløger, J. (2021). Politics, planning, and ruling: the art of taming public participation. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13563475.2021.1883422>, 26(4), 426–440. Retrieved 28 April 2023 from <https://doi.org/10.1080/13563475.2021.1883422>

- Schweizer, P. J., Renn, O., Köck, W., Bovet, J., Benighaus, C., Scheel, O., & Schröter, R. (2016). Public participation for infrastructure planning in the context of the German “Energiewende”. *Utilities Policy*, 43, 206–209. Retrieved 28 April 2023 from <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JUP.2014.07.005>
- Stone, D. A. (1989). Causal Stories and the Formation of Policy Agendas. *Political Science Quarterly*, 104(2), 281. Retrieved 28 April 2023 from <https://doi.org/10.2307/2151585>
- SUBCUSA. (2020). Officials Break Ground on TxDOT'S Clear Lanes Project - SubContractors USA. Retrieved 29 April 2023, from <https://subcusa.com/officials-break-ground-on-txdots-clear-lanes-project/>
- Texas Central. (2020). Environmental Impact Statement Advances Texas High-Speed Train Project. Retrieved 7 May 2023, from <https://www.texascentral.com/posts/environmental-impact-statement-advances-texas-high-speed-train-project/>
- Texas Central. (2023). Learn The Facts - Texas Central. Retrieved 28 April 2023, from <https://www.texascentral.com/facts/>
- TxDOT. (2016). Texas Clear Lanes Congestion Relief Initiative. Retrieved 29 April 2023 from
- TxDOT. (2020). Texas Transportation Plan 2050 (TTP 2050). Retrieved 29 April 2023 from
- TxDOT. (2021). Operating Budget for Fiscal Year 2022.
- TxDOT. (2023). Public Transportation Division. Retrieved 29 April 2023, from <https://www.txdot.gov/about/divisions/public-transportation-division.html>
- U.S. Census Bureau. (2022). U.S. Census Bureau QuickFacts: Texas. Retrieved 29 April 2023, from <https://www.census.gov/quickfacts/TX>
- U.S. Department of Transportation. (2023). Federal Register :: Advancing High-Speed Rail Projects Intended for Operations Over 160 Miles Per Hour Through Domestic Sourcing Plans and Buy America Compliance. Retrieved 28 April 2023, from <https://www.federalregister.gov/documents/2023/03/22/2023-05874/advancing-high-speed-rail-projects-intended-for-operations-over-160-miles-per-hour-through-domestic>
- Wendell Cox. (2022). Texas High Speed Rail: The End or Not? | Newgeography.com. Retrieved 28 April 2023, from <http://www.newgeography.com/content/007597-texas-high-speed-rail-the-end-or-not>